

C-SCALE

D1.5 Data Management Plan (Update)

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Lead Participant:	EODC	Lead Author:	Charis Chatzikyriakou
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Deliverable Abstract

This document provides an updated report on the data types that are collected and generated per Work Package (WP), whether they will be shared with the public and how, whether they can be reused and how, and how they will be preserved during and after the end of the project. The first version of the Data Management Plan, submitted in March 2022 to the EC, included the information on the aforementioned topics until March 2022, while in this second and last version, in addition to the above, information on the data that the onboarded use cases collected and generated is provided as well as on the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) of C-SCALE data is included.

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DELIVERY SLIP

Date	Name	Partner/Activity
Lead Author:	Charis Chatzikyriakou (CC)	EODC
Contributors:	Zdeněk Šustr (ZS)	CESNET
	Enol Fernández (EF)	EGI Foundation
	Björn Backeberg (BB)	Deltares
	Sebastian Luna-Valero (SLV)	EGI Foundation
Moderated by:	Charis Chatzikyriakou (CC)	EODC
Reviewed by:	Xavier Salazar Forn (XSF)	EGI Foundation
	Richard Kidd (RK)	EODC
Approved by:	C-SCALE Activity Management Board (AMB): Christian Briese (CB), Diego Scardaci (DS), Charis Chatzikyriakou (CC), Zdeněk Šustr (ZS), Enol Fernández (EF), Björn Backeberg (BB), Sebastian Luna-Valero (SLV)	EODC, CESNET, EGI Foundation, Deltares

DOCUMENT LOG

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V0.1	12/01/2023	Deliverable document was created	CC
V0.2	24/02/2023	First complete draft	CC, ZS, EF, BB, SLV, external use cases' Pls
V0.3	06/03/2023	Integrated reviewers' feedback	CC, XSF, RK
V0.4	08/03/2023	Integrated feedback from the C-SCALE AMB	CC
V1.0	12/03/2023	Version approved by AMB	C-SCALE AMB

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AMB	Activity Management Board
ARD	Analysis Ready Data
ASL	Apache Software License
AUL	Acceptable Use Policy
CC-BY-NC	Creative Commons NonCommercial license
CF	Climate and Forecast
CGLS	Copernicus Global Land Service
CIF	Crystallographic Information File
CIF	Crystallographic Information File
CMIP6	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6
CORINE	Coordination of information on the environment
C-SCALE	Copernicus – eoSC AnaLytics Engine
DG ENV	Directorate-General for Environment
DIAS	Data and Information Access Services
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
EEA	European Environment Agency
EO	Earth Observation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA5	ECMWF Reanalysis 5th Generation
EUDAT	European Data Infrastructure
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability
FITS	Flexible Image Transport System

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GeoTIFF	Geographic Tagged Image File Format
GEP	Geohazards Exploitation Platform
GLIMS	Global Land Ice Measurements from Space
GPL	GNU General Public License
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GSI	Geological Survey Ireland
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
JRC	Joint Research Centre
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MB	Megabyte
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
NDMI	Normalized Difference Moisture Index
netCDF	network Common Data Form
ODbL	Open Data Commons Open Database License
OLA	Operational Level Agreement
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
PB	Petabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
RTF	Rich Text Format
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SPSS	Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
SRAM	SURF Research Access Management
STAC	SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VA	Virtual Access
WP	Work Package
XML	Extensible Markup Language

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Executive summary

The C-SCALE (Copernicus – eoSC AnaLytics Engine) project brings together European commercial (e.g., Copernicus DIAS) and public data, computing and storage providers to deliver a federated infrastructure to support the Copernicus and Earth Observation (EO) user community. The project participates in the European Commission’s (EC) Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP) and is therefore required to maintain and deliver a Data Management Plan (DMP).

This document provides the second and last version of C-SCALE’s DMP. In the sections below, the data types that are collected, generated and processed in the five Work Packages (WP) of the project from its start and until present (M26) are listed. Their characteristics, the FAIR principles that apply to them - and how – as well as their Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) are detailed based on the DMP template provided by the EC and the Argos DMP platform.

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1 Introduction

The Open Research Data Pilot is run by the EC with the main objective to improve and maximise the access and re-use of research data generated by Horizon 2020 projects. The ORDP promotes the FAIR principles, according to which the research data should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable, and covers two major categories of data:

- the data needed to validate the project results presented in scientific publications, including the associated metadata,
- any other data, e.g., curated data not directly attributable to a publication, or raw data, including the associated metadata.

C-SCALE participates in this pilot, and with the present deliverable, which is the second and last version, it is intended to provide a Data Management Plan for all data that are needed for the validation of the project results as presented in the scientific publications. More specifically, this DMP aims to provide information on the data management life cycle of all data generated, collected and processed within the project.

Therefore, this document provides information on the data types that are collected or generated per Work Package (WP), whether they will be shared with the public and how, whether they can be reused and how, how they will be preserved during and after the end of the project as well their IPRs. Initially, it was decided to use the open platform for Data Management Planning, Argos¹, created by OpenAIRE² and EUDAT³. Argos allows its users to create actionable DMPs that can be easily exchanged among infrastructures, making it a very useful tool for H2020 projects. However, since C-SCALE focuses on federating services rather than producing research data, it soon became obvious that the DMP template had to be simplified and adjusted to the project needs. The template used in this document has been created based on the one provided by the EC and the one used in Argos and adjusted to the characteristics of the data types used by C-SCALE. It is arranged in the following topics:

- High-level description
- Data summary
 - Types of data, purpose of data collection/generation, data formats and standards, origin of data, expected data volume, data utility, scientific impact
- Data FAIRness
 - Metadata, openly accessible data, repositories, and preservation of openly accessible data, reusable data and their purpose, repositories, and preservation of reusable data
- Intellectual Property Rights
 - Ownership, confidentiality, type of IPR and access license

¹ <https://argos.openaire.eu/splash/index.html>

² <https://www.openaire.eu/>

³ <https://www.eudat.eu/>

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In March 2022, a first version of the DMP⁴ was submitted. After that, it was maintained as a living document, and it was updated every time there was a significant change or addition during the runtime of the project. This second version contains all these updates and additions, i.e., the Data Management Plan of the most mature external use cases⁵ and information on the Intellectual Property Rights of the C-SCALE data. It shall be noted that the open access to scientific peer-reviewed publications is obligatory for all Horizon 2020 projects, and therefore they are not subject of the ORDP.

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6363615>

⁵ The external use cases were onboarded in C-SCALE through the project's Open Call.

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2 Data Management Plan per Work Package

2.1 WP1 Project Management

Main contact person	Charis Chatzikyriakou
Description	Data collected and generated to perform the Project Management activities according to the Grant Agreement and enable the communication and collaboration amongst the project members.
Data Summary	
Types of data	<input type="checkbox"/> Observational (e.g., sensor data, data from surveys) <input type="checkbox"/> Simulation (e.g., climate modelling data) <input type="checkbox"/> Derived or compiled (e.g., text mining, 3D models) <input type="checkbox"/> Reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project documentation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ In C- SCALE space in EGI Confluence: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Contracts, and documents/guidelines related to the implementation of the project, incl. official reporting documents ▪ Plans and procedures, KPIs and metrics, risk registry ▪ Project and Board meeting material (agendas, Minutes of meeting, JIRA tickets) • Project deliverables stored in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ C- SCALE space in EGI Confluence (the confidential ones) ○ the C-SCALE Community⁶ in Zenodo⁷ • Personal data, i.e., names and e-mail addresses: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ For project communication, stored in the C- SCALE space in EGI Confluence, EODC's mailing list platform and MS Teams administration ○ For project collaboration, stored in EGI's Confluence • Effort and financial data of project partners collected in EU-Fin platform
Purpose of data collection/generation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To obtain information <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To share information <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To keep on record <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To make informed decisions <input type="checkbox"/> To develop a product

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/communities/c-scale/?page=1&size=20>

⁷ <https://zenodo.org/>

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	<input type="checkbox"/> To improve a product <input type="checkbox"/> To combine with other data The data collection and generation under this WP support the project management and the consortium during the implementation of the project.
Data formats and standards	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Text files - MS Word docs, .txt files, PDF, RTF, XML (Extensible Markup Language) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Numerical - SPSS, Stata, Excel <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Multimedia - jpg / jpeg, gif, tiff, png, mpeg, mp4, QuickTime <input type="checkbox"/> Models – 3D, statistical <input type="checkbox"/> Software – Java, C, Python <input type="checkbox"/> Discipline specific formats - Flexible Image Transport System (FITS) in astronomy, Crystallographic Information File (CIF) for crystallography
Origin of data ⁸	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Primary data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Secondary data All data are either collected from project partners or generated by the Project Management team. Exceptions to this are the plans and procedures that were reused from previous projects and adjusted to the needs of C-SCALE.
Expected data volume	100 MB (megabyte)
Data utility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Research communities <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Decision makers <input type="checkbox"/> Education <input type="checkbox"/> Economy <input type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Industry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other: Project Management team and consortium
Scientific impact	The public project deliverables that are openly accessible via Zenodo can be used by the scientific communities.
Data FAIRness	
Metadata	Public project deliverables accompanied with metadata specific to publication system (author, dates, license information etc. in Zenodo)
Openly accessible data	Public project deliverables

⁸ Primary data is data that have been collected for the first time and have not undergone through data processing and/or analysis, yet. Secondary data is data that have been cleaned up, analysed and shared by others (published or unpublished) and they are those that are being typically reused. Source: Argos (argos.openaire.eu).

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Repositories of openly accessible data	https://zenodo.org/communities/c-scale/?page=1&size=20			
Preservation of openly accessible data	Unlimited			
Reusable data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project documentation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ In C- SCALE space in EGI Confluence: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Guidelines related to the implementation of the project ▪ Plans and procedures • Project deliverables stored in Zenodo 			
Purpose	<input type="checkbox"/> To reproduce and validate findings <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To compare and combine with other data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To follow-up research on a specific area <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To develop new products/services <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other: Implementation guidelines, plans and procedures can be adjusted accordingly and reused in future projects. Project deliverables can be reused both for scientific and Project Management purposes.			
Repositories of reusable data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • C- SCALE space in EGI Confluence • https://zenodo.org/communities/c-scale/?page=1&size=20 			
Preservation of reusable data	Available from the moment they are created and preserved for at least 5 years after the end of the project.			
Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)				
<i>Item</i>	<i>Partners owners & Other beneficiaries involved</i>	<i>Confidential</i>	<i>Type of protection or licensing action used</i>	<i>Protection or licensing actions used</i>
Project deliverables in Zenodo	C-SCALE Consortium	No	Copyright	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project documentation • Confidential deliverables in the C-SCALE space in Confluence • Personal data 	C-SCALE Consortium	Yes	Copyright	N/A

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• Effort and financial data in EU-Fin				
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2.2 WP2 Copernicus Data Federation

Main contact person	Zdeněk Šustr
Description	Data Federation documentation: documentation of services and procedures in the C-SCALE Data federation
Data Summary	
Types of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Observational (e.g., sensor data, data from surveys) <input type="checkbox"/> Simulation (e.g., climate modelling data) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Derived or compiled (e.g., text mining, 3D models) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Detailed STAC metadata derived from Sentinel product manifests <input type="checkbox"/> Reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> User documentation, admin documentation stored in the C-SCALE space in Confluence and README documents in GitHub repositories Source code, Central service configuration stored in GitHub
Purpose of data collection/generation	<input type="checkbox"/> To obtain information <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To share information <input type="checkbox"/> To keep on record <input type="checkbox"/> To make informed decisions <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To develop a product <input type="checkbox"/> To improve a product <input type="checkbox"/> To combine with other data Documentation targeted at users and services administrators.
Data formats and standards	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Text files - MS Word docs, .txt files, PDF, RTF, XML (Extensible Markup Language) <input type="checkbox"/> Numerical - SPSS, Stata, Excel <input type="checkbox"/> Multimedia - jpg / jpeg, gif, tiff, png, mpeg, mp4, QuickTime <input type="checkbox"/> Models – 3D, statistical <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Software – Java, C, Python <input type="checkbox"/> Discipline specific formats - Flexible Image Transport System (FITS) in astronomy, Crystallographic Information File (CIF) for crystallography Plain text (source code, configuration files), or widely established documentation text formats

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Origin of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Primary data <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary data			
Expected data volume	MB (megabyte)			
Data utility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Research communities <input type="checkbox"/> Decision makers <input type="checkbox"/> Education <input type="checkbox"/> Economy <input type="checkbox"/> Public <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Industry <input type="checkbox"/> Other:			
Scientific impact	N/A.			
Data FAIRness				
Metadata	3 rd -party metadata accompanying Earth Observation products are reformatted into another format (STAC) and adjusted to C-SCALE federation prefixes for download.			
Openly accessible data	Open-source code in public repositories, documentation publicly available on the Internet.			
Repositories of openly accessible data	Open-source code repositories (GitHub), open concurrent version system			
Preservation of openly accessible data	Available immediately upon creation, preserved at least until July 2028.			
Reusable data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Source code reusable for developing similar software components, for future contributors, etc. • Documentation reusable in community-specific extensions 			
Purpose	<input type="checkbox"/> To reproduce and validate findings <input type="checkbox"/> To compare and combine with other data <input type="checkbox"/> To follow-up research on a specific area <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To develop new products/services <input type="checkbox"/> Other:			
Repositories of reusable data	GitHub, C-SCALE Wiki			
Preservation of reusable data	Reusable data (source code, documentation) will be preserved at least until July 2028			
Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)				
<i>Item</i>	<i>Partners owners & Other beneficiaries involved</i>	<i>Confidential</i>	<i>Type of protection or licensing action used</i>	<i>Protection or licensing actions used</i>

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Integration components developed for C-SCALE partners	CESNET, EODC, VITO, GRNET, CloudFerro	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Copyright • Open Source 	All components are released under open software licenses, typically ASL 2.0, GPL or MIT
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2.3 WP3 Copernicus Compute Federation

Main contact person	Enol Fernández				
Description	Documentation related to the C-SCALE Compute federation and data collected and generated for its operations.				
Data Summary					
Types of data	<input type="checkbox"/> Observational (e.g., sensor data, data from surveys) <input type="checkbox"/> Simulation (e.g., climate modelling data) <input type="checkbox"/> Derived or compiled (e.g., text mining, 3D models) <input type="checkbox"/> Reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User information for providing access to the providers in EGI Check-in and SRAM • In C-SCALE space in EGI Confluence: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ VA installations' information (description, technology, resource amount, contacts) ○ VA metrics to monitor the usage of installations as defined in the project ○ OLAs/SLAs/AUPs for service delivery ○ Documentation and guidelines ○ Project meeting information, i.e., agendas, attendees, minutes of meeting • Configuration files in the C-SCALE Community in GitHub 				
Purpose of data collection/generation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To obtain information <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To share information <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To keep on record <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To make informed decisions <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To develop a product <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To improve a product <input type="checkbox"/> To combine with other data				
Data formats and standards	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Text files - MS Word docs, .txt files, PDF, RTF, XML (Extensible Markup Language) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Numerical - SPSS, Stata, Excel <input type="checkbox"/> Multimedia - jpg / jpeg, gif, tiff, png, mpeg, mp4, QuickTime				
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	<input type="checkbox"/> Models – 3D, statistical <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Software – Java, C, Python <input type="checkbox"/> Discipline specific formats - Flexible Image Transport System (FITS) in astronomy, Crystallographic Information File (CIF) for crystallography			
Origin of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Primary data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Secondary data Created as a result of work done within the project.			
Expected data volume	MB			
Data utility	<input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Research communities <input type="checkbox"/> Decision makers <input type="checkbox"/> Education <input type="checkbox"/> Economy <input type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Industry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other: Participants within the project and collaborators			
Scientific impact	N/A.			
Data FAIRness				
Metadata	N/A.			
Openly accessible data	Open-source code in public repositories, documentation publicly available on the Internet.			
Repositories of openly accessible data	Open-source code repositories (GitHub), open concurrent version system			
Preservation of openly accessible data	Available immediately upon creation, preserved at least until July 2028.			
Reusable data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Configuration files • Documentation and guidelines 			
Purpose	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To reproduce and validate findings <input type="checkbox"/> To compare and combine with other data <input type="checkbox"/> To follow-up research on a specific area <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To develop new products/services <input type="checkbox"/> Other:			
Repositories of reusable data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • C-SCALE Community in GitHub and dedicated product repositories in GitHub • C- SCALE space in EGI Confluence 			
Preservation of reusable data	Available from the moment they are created and preserved for at least 5 years after the end of the project.			
Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)				
<i>Item</i>	<i>Partners owners & Other beneficiaries involved</i>	<i>Confidential</i>	<i>Type of protection or licensing action used</i>	<i>Protection or licensing actions used</i>

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PaaS Orchestrator templates	INFN	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Copyright • Open Source 	Apache License 2.0
openEO	VITO EODC	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Copyright • Open Source 	Apache License 2.0
SRAMsync	SURF	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Copyright • Open Source 	GNU General Public License v3.0
Notebooks code related to C-SCALE	CESNET	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Copyright • Open Source 	Apache License 2.0

2.4 WP4 User co-design and functional testing of Copernicus data and compute federation

Main contact person	Björn Backeberg								
Description	Use case input and output data: WP4 is responsible for deploying use cases on the C-SCALE federation to test its usability and functional design and feedback via the User Forum to the C-SCALE federated infrastructure providers on how to improve its implementation. The use cases ingest Copernicus data to produce a result or output.								
Data Summary									
Types of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Observational (e.g., sensor data, data from surveys) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Simulation (e.g., climate modelling data) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Derived or compiled (e.g., text mining, 3D models) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures) <input type="checkbox"/> Other:								
	<p>Data from satellite remote sensing platforms, in situ observation networks and (data assimilative) numerical model simulations will be used and generated. The necessary data are sourced from within the federation when available, and if not, from the original source. The data are then stored at the providers supporting the use cases.</p> <p>The input and output data per use case are:</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <thead> <tr> <th>Use case</th> <th>Input data</th> <th>Output data</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td> </td> <td> </td> <td> </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Use case	Input data	Output data			
Use case	Input data	Output data							

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	Land Surface Drought Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hydro-MERIT • HydroLAKES • Global Reservoir and Dam Database (GRanD) • MODIS/Terra Leaf Area Index • CORINE Land Cover • SoilGrids • Global Land Ice Measurements from Space (GLIMS) • ERA5 reanalysis • SEAS5 seasonal forecast 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model river discharge time series • Model discharge anomaly time series • Model soil moisture anomaly maps
	Aquamonitor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sentinel-2 L1C 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Derived land surface change maps
	WaterWatch	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sentinel-2 L1C • JRC Water Occurrence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Derived time series of reservoir surface water area • Derived maps of surface water extent for analysed reservoirs
	HiSea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global Ocean Physics Reanalysis • Global ocean biogeochemistry hindcast • ERA5 • FES2012 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model maps of ocean physics forecasts. • Model maps of ocean biogeochemistry forecasts.
	RETURN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sentinel-1 ARD – Flattening Gamma • Sentinel-2 Surface Reflectance • Landsat-8 Surface Reflectance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Derived maps of tropical forest recovery capacity • Derived statistics of tropical forest recovery capacity

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	Wetland Water Stresses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sentinel-1 γ_0^T • Sentinel-1 σ_0 • CORINE Land Cover • Sentinel-2 L2A • RAMSAR sites • Natura2000 areas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Derived maps about the impact of designating protection zones on wetland behaviour
Purpose of data collection/generation	<input type="checkbox"/> To obtain information <input type="checkbox"/> To share information <input type="checkbox"/> To keep on record <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To make informed decisions <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To develop a product <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To improve a product <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To combine with other data The use cases ingest a variety of EO and Copernicus data to generate products/results through analytics and/or modelling.		
Data formats and standards	<input type="checkbox"/> Text files - MS Word docs, .txt files, PDF, RTF, XML (Extensible Markup Language) <input type="checkbox"/> Numerical - SPSS, Stata, Excel <input type="checkbox"/> Multimedia - jpg / jpeg, gif, tiff, png, mpeg, mp4, QuickTime <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Models – 3D, statistical <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Software – Java, C, Python <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Discipline specific formats - Flexible Image Transport System (FITS) in astronomy, Crystallographic Information File (CIF) for crystallography Geospatial data; Image data; NetCDF and Cloud Optimised GeoTIFFs are commonly used data formats.		
Origin of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Primary data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Secondary data		
Expected data volume	PB (petabyte) Global scale analytics require PB-scale data volumes.		
Data utility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Research communities <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Decision makers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Education <input type="checkbox"/> Economy <input type="checkbox"/> Public <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Industry <input type="checkbox"/> Other		

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	The Copernicus data delivered via the C-SCALE federation will facilitate the development of downstream data analytics, data fusion, platforms, applications and services.																
Scientific impact	It is not anticipated that the work in WP4 will result in scientific impact. The use cases deployed, have a relatively high TRL, and as such have already been published in the peer-reviewed literature.																
Data FAIRness																	
Metadata	Typically, the CF-compliant metadata standard is used																
Openly accessible data	<p>The use cases use a number of openly accessible datasets, which are listed, with their licenses, in the following:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Input Data</th> <th>License</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Hydro-MERIT</td> <td>CC-BY-NC 4.0 license: Non-Commercial Use with less restriction. ODbL 1.0 license: Commercial Use is OK, but the derived data based on MERIT Hydro should be made publicly available under the same ODbL license</td> </tr> <tr> <td>HydroLAKES</td> <td>CC-BY-NC 4.0 license</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Global Reservoir and Dam Database (GRanD)</td> <td>Free for non-commercial use https://globaldamwatch.org/data/</td> </tr> <tr> <td>MODIS/Terra Leaf Area Index</td> <td>Public: This dataset is intended for public access and use. License: No license information was provided. If this work was prepared by an officer or employee of the United States government as part of that person's official duties it is considered a U.S. Government Work. https://catalog.data.gov/dataset/modis-terra-leaf-area-index-fpar-8-day-l4-global-500m-sin-grid-v006</td> </tr> <tr> <td>CORINE Land Cover</td> <td>Access to data is based on a principle of full, open and free access as established by the Copernicus data and information policy Regulation (EU) No 1159/2013 of 12 July 2013 https://land.copernicus.eu/faq/about-data-access</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SoilGrids</td> <td>CC-BY 4.0 License. https://www.isric.org/explore/soilgrids</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Global Land Ice Measurements from Space (GLIMS)</td> <td>Attribution 4.0 International license (CC BY 4.0). https://www.glims.org/RGI/</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Input Data	License	Hydro-MERIT	CC-BY-NC 4.0 license: Non-Commercial Use with less restriction. ODbL 1.0 license: Commercial Use is OK, but the derived data based on MERIT Hydro should be made publicly available under the same ODbL license	HydroLAKES	CC-BY-NC 4.0 license	Global Reservoir and Dam Database (GRanD)	Free for non-commercial use https://globaldamwatch.org/data/	MODIS/Terra Leaf Area Index	Public: This dataset is intended for public access and use. License: No license information was provided. If this work was prepared by an officer or employee of the United States government as part of that person's official duties it is considered a U.S. Government Work. https://catalog.data.gov/dataset/modis-terra-leaf-area-index-fpar-8-day-l4-global-500m-sin-grid-v006	CORINE Land Cover	Access to data is based on a principle of full, open and free access as established by the Copernicus data and information policy Regulation (EU) No 1159/2013 of 12 July 2013 https://land.copernicus.eu/faq/about-data-access	SoilGrids	CC-BY 4.0 License. https://www.isric.org/explore/soilgrids	Global Land Ice Measurements from Space (GLIMS)	Attribution 4.0 International license (CC BY 4.0). https://www.glims.org/RGI/
Input Data	License																
Hydro-MERIT	CC-BY-NC 4.0 license: Non-Commercial Use with less restriction. ODbL 1.0 license: Commercial Use is OK, but the derived data based on MERIT Hydro should be made publicly available under the same ODbL license																
HydroLAKES	CC-BY-NC 4.0 license																
Global Reservoir and Dam Database (GRanD)	Free for non-commercial use https://globaldamwatch.org/data/																
MODIS/Terra Leaf Area Index	Public: This dataset is intended for public access and use. License: No license information was provided. If this work was prepared by an officer or employee of the United States government as part of that person's official duties it is considered a U.S. Government Work. https://catalog.data.gov/dataset/modis-terra-leaf-area-index-fpar-8-day-l4-global-500m-sin-grid-v006																
CORINE Land Cover	Access to data is based on a principle of full, open and free access as established by the Copernicus data and information policy Regulation (EU) No 1159/2013 of 12 July 2013 https://land.copernicus.eu/faq/about-data-access																
SoilGrids	CC-BY 4.0 License. https://www.isric.org/explore/soilgrids																
Global Land Ice Measurements from Space (GLIMS)	Attribution 4.0 International license (CC BY 4.0). https://www.glims.org/RGI/																

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	ERA5 reanalysis	https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/api/v2/terms/statistic/licence-to-use-copernicus-products.pdf
	SEAS5 seasonal forecast	CEMS-FLOODS datasets licence https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/api/v2/terms/statistic/cems-floods.pdf
	Sentinel-2 L1C	Sentinel Data Terms and Conditions
	JRC Water Occurrence	All data here is produced under the Copernicus Programme and is provided free of charge, without restriction of use. For the full license information see the Copernicus Regulation. https://www.copernicus.eu/en/about-copernicus/international-cooperation
	Global Ocean Physics Reanalysis	https://marine.copernicus.eu/user-corner/service-commitments-and-licence
	Global ocean biogeochemistry hindcast	https://marine.copernicus.eu/user-corner/service-commitments-and-licence
	FES2012	https://www.aviso.altimetry.fr/fileadmin/documents/data/License_Aviso.pdf
	Sentinel-1 ARD - Sigma	Sentinel Data Terms and Conditions
	Sentinel-1 ARD – Flattening Gamma	Sentinel Data Terms and Conditions
	Sentinel-2 Surface Reflectance	Sentinel Data Terms and Conditions
	Landsat-8 Surface Reflectance	https://www.usgs.gov/information-policies-and-instructions/copyrights-and-credits
	Sentinel-1 γ_0^T	Sentinel Data Terms and Conditions
	Sentinel-2 L2A	Sentinel Data Terms and Conditions
	RAMSAR sites	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0
	Natura2000 areas	EEA standard re-use policy: unless otherwise indicated, re-use of content on the EEA website for commercial or non-commercial purposes is permitted free of charge, provided that the source is acknowledged (https://www.eea.europa.eu/legal/copyright).

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	<table border="1" data-bbox="512 259 1380 338"> <tr> <td data-bbox="512 259 699 338"></td> <td data-bbox="699 259 1380 338">Copyright holder: Directorate-General for Environment (DG ENV).</td> </tr> </table> <p data-bbox="512 376 1388 656">The use case output data is stored on storage resources of the provider supporting the use case. Some of the use cases deliver forecast data (e.g. LSDA and HiSea) as outputs, these are stored on the providers and can be made available to interested users. Other use cases deliver Jupyter Notebooks offering EO-based data analytics (e.g. Aquamonitor and WaterWatch). For the use cases delivering Jupyter Notebooks, the Jupyter Notebooks are openly available for use and adaptation from the C-SCALE community Github repository.</p> <p data-bbox="512 696 1388 763">Note that offering data services to stakeholders is not the focus of the use cases in the C-SCALE project.</p>		Copyright holder: Directorate-General for Environment (DG ENV).																										
	Copyright holder: Directorate-General for Environment (DG ENV).																												
Repositories of openly accessible data	<table border="1" data-bbox="512 801 1380 1886"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="512 801 735 835">Input Data</th> <th data-bbox="735 801 1380 835">URL</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="512 835 735 913">Hydro-MERIT</td> <td data-bbox="735 835 1380 913">http://hydro.iis.u-tokyo.ac.jp/~yamada/MERIT_Hydro/</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="512 913 735 947">HydroLAKES</td> <td data-bbox="735 913 1380 947">https://www.hydrosheds.org/page/hydrolakes</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="512 947 735 1093">Global Reservoir and Dam Database (GRanD)</td> <td data-bbox="735 947 1380 1093">https://globaldamwatch.org/grand/</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="512 1093 735 1171">MODIS/Terra Leaf Area Index</td> <td data-bbox="735 1093 1380 1171">https://ladsweb.modaps.eosdis.nasa.gov/missions-and-measurements/products/MOD15A2/</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="512 1171 735 1249">CORINE Land Cover</td> <td data-bbox="735 1171 1380 1249">https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="512 1249 735 1283">SoilGrids</td> <td data-bbox="735 1249 1380 1283">https://www.isric.org/explore/soilgrids</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="512 1283 735 1429">Global Land Ice Measurements from Space (GLIMS)</td> <td data-bbox="735 1283 1380 1429">https://www.glims.org/</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="512 1429 735 1496">ERA5 reanalysis</td> <td data-bbox="735 1429 1380 1496">https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/datasets/reanalysis-datasets/era5</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="512 1496 735 1563">SEAS5 seasonal forecast</td> <td data-bbox="735 1496 1380 1563">https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/documentation-and-support/long-range</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="512 1563 735 1597">Sentinel-2 L1C</td> <td data-bbox="735 1563 1380 1597">Access to Sentinel Data</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="512 1597 735 1675">JRC Water Occurrence</td> <td data-bbox="735 1597 1380 1675">https://global-surface-water.appspot.com/download</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="512 1675 735 1787">Global Ocean Physics Reanalysis</td> <td data-bbox="735 1675 1380 1787">https://resources.marine.copernicus.eu/product-download/GLOBAL_REANALYSIS_PHY_001_030</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="512 1787 735 1886">Global ocean biogeochemistry hindcast</td> <td data-bbox="735 1787 1380 1886">https://resources.marine.copernicus.eu/product-download/GLOBAL_REANALYSIS_BIO_001_029</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Input Data	URL	Hydro-MERIT	http://hydro.iis.u-tokyo.ac.jp/~yamada/MERIT_Hydro/	HydroLAKES	https://www.hydrosheds.org/page/hydrolakes	Global Reservoir and Dam Database (GRanD)	https://globaldamwatch.org/grand/	MODIS/Terra Leaf Area Index	https://ladsweb.modaps.eosdis.nasa.gov/missions-and-measurements/products/MOD15A2/	CORINE Land Cover	https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover	SoilGrids	https://www.isric.org/explore/soilgrids	Global Land Ice Measurements from Space (GLIMS)	https://www.glims.org/	ERA5 reanalysis	https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/datasets/reanalysis-datasets/era5	SEAS5 seasonal forecast	https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/documentation-and-support/long-range	Sentinel-2 L1C	Access to Sentinel Data	JRC Water Occurrence	https://global-surface-water.appspot.com/download	Global Ocean Physics Reanalysis	https://resources.marine.copernicus.eu/product-download/GLOBAL_REANALYSIS_PHY_001_030	Global ocean biogeochemistry hindcast	https://resources.marine.copernicus.eu/product-download/GLOBAL_REANALYSIS_BIO_001_029
Input Data	URL																												
Hydro-MERIT	http://hydro.iis.u-tokyo.ac.jp/~yamada/MERIT_Hydro/																												
HydroLAKES	https://www.hydrosheds.org/page/hydrolakes																												
Global Reservoir and Dam Database (GRanD)	https://globaldamwatch.org/grand/																												
MODIS/Terra Leaf Area Index	https://ladsweb.modaps.eosdis.nasa.gov/missions-and-measurements/products/MOD15A2/																												
CORINE Land Cover	https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover																												
SoilGrids	https://www.isric.org/explore/soilgrids																												
Global Land Ice Measurements from Space (GLIMS)	https://www.glims.org/																												
ERA5 reanalysis	https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/datasets/reanalysis-datasets/era5																												
SEAS5 seasonal forecast	https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/documentation-and-support/long-range																												
Sentinel-2 L1C	Access to Sentinel Data																												
JRC Water Occurrence	https://global-surface-water.appspot.com/download																												
Global Ocean Physics Reanalysis	https://resources.marine.copernicus.eu/product-download/GLOBAL_REANALYSIS_PHY_001_030																												
Global ocean biogeochemistry hindcast	https://resources.marine.copernicus.eu/product-download/GLOBAL_REANALYSIS_BIO_001_029																												

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	FES2012	https://www.aviso.altimetry.fr/es/data/products/auxiliary-products/global-tide-fes/description-fes2012.html
	Sentinel-1 ARD - Sigma	https://scihub.copernicus.eu/
	Sentinel-1 ARD – Flattening Gamma	https://scihub.copernicus.eu/
	Sentinel-2 Surface Reflectance	https://scihub.copernicus.eu/
	Landsat-8 Surface Reflectance	https://www.usgs.gov/landsat-missions/landsat-data-access
	Sentinel-1 γ_0^T	https://scihub.copernicus.eu/
	Sentinel-2 L2A	https://scihub.copernicus.eu/
	RAMSAR sites	https://rsis Ramsar.org/
	Natura2000 areas	https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/natura-12
Preservation of openly accessible data	The input data needed will be preserved on the C-SCALE federation for 5 years.	
Reusable data	<p>The openly accessible data listed above – used as input data for the use cases – are also reusable data.</p> <p>As mentioned, some use cases provide forecast data as outputs, and others provide data analytics via Jupyter Notebooks as an output. The Jupyter Notebooks are openly available for use and adaptation from the C-SCALE community Github repository. The forecast data output is stored on the providers and can be made available to stakeholders upon request.</p> <p>Note that offering data services to stakeholders is not the focus of the use cases in the C-SCALE project.</p>	
Purpose	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To reproduce and validate findings <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To compare and combine with other data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To follow-up research on a specific area <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To develop new products/services <input type="checkbox"/> Other:	
Repositories of reusable data	See “Repositories of openly accessible data”.	
Preservation of reusable data	See “Preservation of openly accessible data”.	
Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)		

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<i>Item</i>	<i>Partners owners & Other beneficiaries involved</i>	<i>Confidential</i>	<i>Foresee n embargo o date</i>	<i>Type of protection or licensing action used</i>	<i>Protection or licensing actions used</i>
Aquamonitor use case (https://github.com/c-scale-community/use-case-aquamonitor)	Deltares	No	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Copyright • Open Source 	Apache 2.0
LSDA use case (https://github.com/c-scale-community/use-case-high-res-land-surface-drought-analysis)	Deltares	No	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Copyright • Open Source 	Apache 2.0
HiSea use case (https://github.com/c-scale-community/use-case-hisea)	Deltares	No	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Copyright • Open Source 	Apache 2.0
WaterWatch (https://github.com/c-scale-community/use-case-waterwatch)	Deltares	No	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Copyright • Open Source 	Apache 2.0
RETURN use case (https://github.com/c-scale-community/use-case-return)	WUR, IIASA, SURF, EODC	No	2024	Copyright	CC-BY
Wetland water stress use case (https://github.com/c-scale-community/use-case-wetland-water-stress)	TUW	No	June 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Copyright • Open Source 	Apache 2.0

In the sections below, the Data Management Plan of the most mature – at the time of writing – external use cases are provided. These use cases were onboarded in C-SCALE through the project’s Open Call.

2.4.1 Use Case: GLTFCA

Use Case Name	Great Limpopo Trans-Frontier Conservation Area Project Forest disturbance assessment. (GLTFCA) REDD+				
Main contact person	Marius Van Der Vyber: mvandervyver@biocarbonpartners.com ;				
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	Emmanuel Da Ponte: edaponte@biocarbonpartners.com
Description	GLTFCA REDD+ use case input data for the identification of different forest change types, in particular degradation, with the use of the AVOCADO algorithm and resulting output data.
Data Summary	
Types of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Observational (e.g., sensor data, data from surveys) <input type="checkbox"/> Simulation (e.g., climate modelling data) <input type="checkbox"/> Derived or compiled (e.g., text mining, 3D models) <input type="checkbox"/> Reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures) <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify: The goal is to be able to capture levels of degradation and regrowth based on some reference points and a dense time-series NDMI index across the GLTFCA REDD+ feasibility study area. Conventional techniques do not adequately capture particularly forest degradation and forest restoration (regrowth) from satellite data. This algorithm shows promise and could give good spatially-explicit degradation and regrowth across a diverse range of forest types such as is found in Mozambique.
Purpose of data collection/generation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To obtain information <input type="checkbox"/> To share information <input type="checkbox"/> To keep on record <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To make informed decisions <input type="checkbox"/> To develop a product <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To improve a product <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To combine with other data
Data formats and standards	<input type="checkbox"/> Text files - MS Word docs, .txt files, PDF, RTF, XML (Extensible Markup Language) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Numerical - SPSS, Stata, Excel <input type="checkbox"/> Multimedia - jpg / jpeg, gif, tiff, png, mpeg, mp4, QuickTime <input type="checkbox"/> Models – 3D, statistical <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Software – Java, C, Python <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Discipline specific formats - Flexible Image Transport System (FITS) in astronomy, Crystallographic Information File (CIF) for crystallography <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:
Origin of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Primary data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Secondary data
Expected data volume	More than 300 GB

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Data utility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Research communities <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Decision makers <input type="checkbox"/> Education <input type="checkbox"/> Economy <input type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Industry <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:			
Scientific impact	The test of the AVOCADO algorithm could be further applied on similar areas across Africa where the company is currently implementing or planning to implement REDD Plus projects (e.g., Zambia and Angola). The tool could further be extrapolated to Governmental institutes, to use as a platform to monitor forest dynamics.			
Data FAIRness				
Metadata	Possibly field data			
Openly accessible data	Landsat, Sentinel, PAL SAR			
Repositories of openly accessible data	Archives from OPTICAL and RADAR sensors			
Preservation of openly accessible data	Field related data would not be accessible or shared.			
Reusable data	N/A			
Purpose	<input type="checkbox"/> To reproduce and validate findings <input type="checkbox"/> To compare and combine with other data <input type="checkbox"/> To follow-up research on a specific area <input type="checkbox"/> To develop new products/services <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:			
Repositories of reusable data	N/A			
Preservation of reusable data	N/A			
Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)				
<i>Item</i>	<i>Partners owners & Other beneficiaries involved</i>	<i>Confidential</i>	<i>Type of protection or licensing action used</i>	<i>Protection or licensing actions used</i>
Degradation layer	BCP	Yes	Copyright	N/A

2.4.2 Use Case: IRGEOS

Use Case Name	IRGEOS (Irish Geoscience Surveys)
Main contact person	Eugene Hickey

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Description	This project uses data from satellite observation (https://scihub.copernicus.eu/) and from the Geological Survey Ireland (https://www.gsi.ie/) to investigate the interplay between geochemical / geophysical features and vegetation cover.
Data Summary	
Types of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Observational (e.g., sensor data, data from surveys) <input type="checkbox"/> Simulation (e.g., climate modelling data) <input type="checkbox"/> Derived or compiled (e.g., text mining, 3D models) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures) <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify: GSI Bedrock 100k (https://www.gsi.ie/en-ie/data-and-maps/Pages/Bedrock.aspx#100k), GSI Tellus Data (https://www.gsi.ie/en-ie/data-and-maps/Pages/Geochemistry.aspx), Sentinel-2 satellite data.
Purpose of data collection/generation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To obtain information <input type="checkbox"/> To share information <input type="checkbox"/> To keep on record <input type="checkbox"/> To make informed decisions <input type="checkbox"/> To develop a product <input type="checkbox"/> To improve a product <input type="checkbox"/> To combine with other data
Data formats and standards	<input type="checkbox"/> Text files - MS Word docs, .txt files, PDF, RTF, XML (Extensible Markup Language) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Numerical - SPSS, Stata, Excel <input type="checkbox"/> Multimedia - jpg / jpeg, gif, tiff, png, mpeg, mp4, QuickTime <input type="checkbox"/> Models – 3D, statistical <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Software – Java, C, Python <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Discipline specific formats - Flexible Image Transport System (FITS) in astronomy, Crystallographic Information File (CIF) for crystallography <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:
Origin of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Primary data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Secondary data
Expected data volume	~ 10GB

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Data utility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Research communities <input type="checkbox"/> Decision makers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Education <input type="checkbox"/> Economy <input type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Industry <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:			
Scientific impact	Deeper understanding of the interplay between ground-based and satellite-based datasets			
Data FAIRness				
Metadata	N/A			
Openly accessible data	All the data used is openly accessible. Any data products and code produced will be openly available. Scientific publications will be available on open access.			
Repositories of openly accessible data	Software will be available on public github repositories (exact location TBD).			
Preservation of openly accessible data	Software produced might not necessarily be maintained but will be available indefinitely.			
Reusable data	Any data products and code produced will be openly available. Scientific publications will be available on open access.			
Purpose	<input type="checkbox"/> To reproduce and validate findings <input type="checkbox"/> To compare and combine with other data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To follow-up research on a specific area <input type="checkbox"/> To develop new products/services <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify: Novel exploratory research			
Repositories of reusable data	Exact location TBD.			
Preservation of reusable data	Unlimited			
Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)				
Item	<i>Partners owners & Other beneficiaries involved</i>	<i>Confidential</i>	<i>Type of protection or licensing action used</i>	<i>Protection or licensing actions used</i>
Data products and code produced.	IRGEOS	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Copyright • Open Source 	N/A

2.4.3 Use Case: KappaMask

Use Case Name	KappaMask, Providing KappaMask-based cloud and cloud segmentation masks for every Sentinel-2 product over Europe.				
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Main contact person	andres.luhamaa@kappazeta.ee
Description	The use case adds cloud-mask data for Sentinel-2 images, including cloud shadows, transparent clouds and clouds. This kind of data is essential for any automated data analytics of Sentinel-2 and currently available cloud masking solutions are not accurate enough for many use cases.
Data Summary	
Types of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Observational (e.g., sensor data, data from surveys) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Simulation (e.g., climate modelling data) <input type="checkbox"/> Derived or compiled (e.g., text mining, 3D models) <input type="checkbox"/> Reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures) <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify: KappaMask provides cloud masks, which are related to actually observed clouds in satellite images.
Purpose of data collection/generation	<input type="checkbox"/> To obtain information <input type="checkbox"/> To share information <input type="checkbox"/> To keep on record <input type="checkbox"/> To make informed decisions <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To develop a product <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To improve a product <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To combine with other data Cloud mask is an input for further data analytics processes, to help data cleaning.
Data formats and standards	<input type="checkbox"/> Text files - MS Word docs, .txt files, PDF, RTF, XML (Extensible Markup Language) <input type="checkbox"/> Numerical - SPSS, Stata, Excel <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Multimedia - jpg / jpeg, gif, tiff, png, mpeg, mp4, QuickTime <input type="checkbox"/> Models – 3D, statistical <input type="checkbox"/> Software – Java, C, Python <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Discipline specific formats - Flexible Image Transport System (FITS) in astronomy, Crystallographic Information File (CIF) for crystallography <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:
Origin of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Primary data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Secondary data The data is complementary to Sentinel-2 data.
Expected data volume	~4TB

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Data utility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Research communities <input type="checkbox"/> Decision makers <input type="checkbox"/> Education <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Economy <input type="checkbox"/> Public <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Industry <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:			
Scientific impact	Increased quality of various land-monitoring products.			
Data FAIRness				
Metadata	GeoTIFF, https://docs.opengeospatial.org/is/19-008r4/19-008r4.html			
Openly accessible data	The data will be made available in CESNET ⁹ cloud, so users who access Sentinel-2 data there will have access to KappaMask products.			
Repositories of openly accessible data	Exact address to be confirmed			
Preservation of openly accessible data	As long as CESNET keeps Sentinel-2 data available.			
Reusable data	Derived cloud-mask data for Sentinel-2 images			
Purpose	<input type="checkbox"/> To reproduce and validate findings <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To compare and combine with other data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To follow-up research on a specific area <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To develop new products/services <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:			
Repositories of reusable data	CESNET cloud			
Preservation of reusable data	As long as CESNET keeps Sentinel-2 data available.			
Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)				
<i>Item</i>	<i>Partners owners & Other beneficiaries involved</i>	<i>Confidential</i>	<i>Type of protection or licensing action used</i>	<i>Protection or licensing actions used</i>
Cloud-mask data for Sentinel-2 images	KappaZeta Ltd	No	• Copyright	N/A

2.4.4 Use Case: LOST-Salvage

Use Case Name	LOST-Salvage
Main contact person	Björn Backeberg <bjorn.backeberg@deltares.nl>

⁹ <https://creodias.eu/>

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Description	<p>The objective of LOST-Salvage is to pilot operational support for salvage operations at sea using Lagrangian Ocean Search Targets (LOST). To this end the use case will download global wind and ocean current hindcast and forecast data on a daily basis, which are used as input data for LOST.</p> <p>The ambition is to enable stakeholders to run LOST simulations anywhere in the global ocean. The ambition is to set up a simple dashboard to facilitate this, either via https://streamlit.io/, or via Jupyter Notebooks combined with https://voila.readthedocs.io/en/stable/.</p> <p>The use case will contribute to testing the C-SCALE federation usability and functional design and will provide feedback via the User Forum to the C-SCALE federated infrastructure providers on how to improve its implementation.</p>
Data Summary	
Types of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Observational (e.g., sensor data, data from surveys) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Simulation (e.g., climate modelling data) <input type="checkbox"/> Derived or compiled (e.g., text mining, 3D models) <input type="checkbox"/> Reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures) <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global Ocean 1/12° Physics Analysis and Forecast updated Daily (https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00016) • ERA5 hourly data on single levels (https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels) • Global Forecast System 0.25 Degree Hourly (https://nomads.ncep.noaa.gov/txt_descriptions/GFS_doc.shtml) • GOFS 3.1: 41-layer HYCOM + NCODA Global 1/12° Analysis (https://www.hycom.org/dataserver/gofs-3pt1/analysis)
Purpose of data collection/generation	<input type="checkbox"/> To obtain information <input type="checkbox"/> To share information <input type="checkbox"/> To keep on record <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To make informed decisions <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To develop a product <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To improve a product <input type="checkbox"/> To combine with other data <p>The hind- and forecast data of winds and ocean surface currents is used as input data for LOST. Based on these data, LOST then returns simulated/forecast trajectories of objects drifting in the ocean. The drift trajectories are used by stakeholders to plan their salvage operations.</p>

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Data formats and standards	<input type="checkbox"/> Text files - MS Word docs, .txt files, PDF, RTF, XML (Extensible Markup Language) <input type="checkbox"/> Numerical - SPSS, Stata, Excel <input type="checkbox"/> Multimedia - jpg / jpeg, gif, tiff, png, mpeg, mp4, QuickTime <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Models – 3D, statistical <input type="checkbox"/> Software – Java, C, Python <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Discipline specific formats - Flexible Image Transport System (FITS) in astronomy, Crystallographic Information File (CIF) for crystallography <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:
Origin of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Primary data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Secondary data
Expected data volume	Order TB
Data utility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Research communities <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Decision makers <input type="checkbox"/> Education <input type="checkbox"/> Economy <input type="checkbox"/> Public <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Industry <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:
Scientific impact	It is not anticipated that this work will generate scientific impact. It is intended to demonstrate the possibilities around running a lightweight operational service for stakeholders involved in marine salvage operations.
Data FAIRness	
Metadata	Typically, the CF-compliant metadata standard is used
Openly accessible data	<p>This use case uses openly accessible datasets. Listed below are their licenses:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global Ocean 1/12° Physics Analysis and Forecast updated Daily: https://marine.copernicus.eu/user-corner/service-commitments-and-licence • ERA5 hourly data on single levels: https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/api/v2/terms/static/licence-to-use-copernicus-products.pdf • Global Forecast System 0.25 Degree Hourly: Open Data. There are no restrictions on the use of this data (https://registry.opendata.aws/noaa-gfs-bdp-pds/). • GOFS 3.1: 41-layer HYCOM + NCODA Global 1/12° Analysis: All hycom data provided is UNCLASSIFIED. DoD DISTRIBUTION A. Approved for Public Release; Distribution Unlimited (https://www.hycom.org/dataserver).
Repositories of openly accessible data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global Ocean 1/12° Physics Analysis and Forecast updated Daily (https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00016)

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ERA5 hourly data on single levels (https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels) Global Forecast System 0.25 Degree Hourly (https://nomads.ncep.noaa.gov/txt_descriptions/GFS_doc.shtml) GOFS 3.1: 41-layer HYCOM + NCODA Global 1/12° Analysis (https://www.hycom.org/dataserver/gofs-3pt1/analysis) 			
Preservation of openly accessible data	For the input wind and ocean surface current data, only the most recent 30 days plus 10-day forecast from present will be stored on the infrastructure. This will be updated daily. All the result LOST simulations including subset input data run by / for stakeholders will be archived for further analysis.			
Reusable data	All the result LOST simulations including subset input data run by / for stakeholders will be archived for further analysis.			
Purpose	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To reproduce and validate findings <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To compare and combine with other data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To follow-up research on a specific area <input type="checkbox"/> To develop new products/services <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:			
Repositories of reusable data	C-SCALE provider to facilitate storage and sharing of reusable data.			
Preservation of reusable data	C-SCALE provider to support preserving the data for up to 5 years after the project.			
Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)				
<i>Item</i>	<i>Partners owners & Other beneficiaries involved</i>	<i>Confidential</i>	<i>Type of protection or licensing action used</i>	<i>Protection or licensing actions used</i>
LOST-Salvage use case	Deltares DGFI, TUM	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Copyright Open Source 	Apache 2.0 for software. Creative Commons BY 4.0 for data.

2.4.5 Use Case: Pangeo@Climate

Use Case Name	Pangeo@Climate
Main contact person	Anne Fouilloux & Tina Odaka
Description	Use cases from the CLIVAR, eScience and NordicESMHub communities. This use case is to answer crucial scientific questions about the past, present or future Arctic climate system, under the guidance of experts in the field. In parallel and using the developed use cases, training material is being developed to empower a new generation of researchers.

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Data Summary	
Types of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Observational (e.g., sensor data, data from surveys) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Simulation (e.g., climate modelling data) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Derived or compiled (e.g., text mining, 3D models) <input type="checkbox"/> Reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures) <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:
Purpose of data collection/generation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To obtain information <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To share information <input type="checkbox"/> To keep on record <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To make informed decisions <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To develop a product <input type="checkbox"/> To improve a product <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To combine with other data Combine arctic subset of CMIP6 data in the cloud in conjunction with other datasets such as satellite observation or in-situ observation available in C-SCALE Copernicus.
Data formats and standards	<input type="checkbox"/> Text files - MS Word docs, .txt files, PDF, RTF, XML (Extensible Markup Language) <input type="checkbox"/> Numerical - SPSS, Stata, Excel <input type="checkbox"/> Multimedia - jpg / jpeg, gif, tiff, png, mpeg, mp4, QuickTime <input type="checkbox"/> Models – 3D, statistical <input type="checkbox"/> Software – Java, C, Python <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Discipline specific formats - Flexible Image Transport System (FITS) in astronomy, Crystallographic Information File (CIF) for crystallography <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:
Origin of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Primary data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Secondary data CMIP6, ERA5 and CLOUDSAT; different studies with one study requiring (global coverage, 2006-2009; for details e.g., variables, etc. see hackmd) and other studies for CLIVAR are details in the CLIVAR hackmd.
Expected data volume	20 TB (if we need to download all the data e.g. not already available on C-SCALE).
Data utility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Research communities <input type="checkbox"/> Decision makers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Education <input type="checkbox"/> Economy <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Industry <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:

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Scientific impact	This use case is to answer crucial scientific questions about the past, present or future Arctic climate system, under the guidance of experts in the field. Without a proper infrastructure these scientific questions cannot be answered easily by researchers.			
Data FAIRness				
Metadata	CF-conventions https://cfconventions.org/ and https://www.cloudsat.cira.colostate.edu/data-products			
Openly accessible data	Some CLOUDSAT Data Sets are not openly accessible yet. All other datasets are openly accessible.			
Repositories of openly accessible data	https://esgf-node.llnl.gov/projects/cmip6/ https://registry.opendata.aws/cmip6/ https://registry.opendata.aws/ecmwf-era5/ https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-pressure-levels?tab=overview https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=overview			
Preservation of openly accessible data	Done by original providers. Newly generated products will be published on Zenodo, Pangaea and other national archives (French, Norwegian, etc.)			
Reusable data	All datasets produced will contain metadata and will be made available on publicly accessible repositories with DOIs. Datasets used in the developed training material will be made available on Zenodo with CC-BY-4 license.			
Purpose	<input type="checkbox"/> To reproduce and validate findings <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To compare and combine with other data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To follow-up research on a specific area <input type="checkbox"/> To develop new products/services <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify: This use case is to answer crucial scientific questions about the past, present or future Arctic climate system, under the guidance of experts in the field. In parallel and using the developed use cases, training material is being developed to empower a new generation of researchers.			
Repositories of reusable data	https://zenodo.org/ https://www.pangaea.de/ https://archive.norstore.no/			
Preservation of reusable data	Each dataset will get a DOI and long-term preservation will be ensured.			
Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)				
<i>Item</i>	<i>Partners owners & Other beneficiaries involved</i>	<i>Confidential</i>	<i>Type of protection or licensing action used</i>	<i>Protection or licensing actions used</i>

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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training datasets • Datasets generated by researchers 	Pangeo community, researchers' institution	No	Copyright	CC-BY-4
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2.4.6 Use Case: Pangeo4Greenness

Use Case Name	Pangeo4Greenness (P4G)			
Main contact person	Pier Lorenzo Marasco pl.marasco@gmail.com			
Description	Copernicus Global Land Service Sentinel-3 Top of Canopy (later on: CGLS S3 TOC)			
Data Summary				
Types of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Observational (e.g., sensor data, data from surveys) <input type="checkbox"/> Simulation (e.g., climate modelling data) <input type="checkbox"/> Derived or compiled (e.g., text mining, 3D models) <input type="checkbox"/> Reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures) <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:			
Purpose of data collection/generation	<input type="checkbox"/> To obtain information <input type="checkbox"/> To share information <input type="checkbox"/> To keep on record <input type="checkbox"/> To make informed decisions <input type="checkbox"/> To develop a product <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To improve a product <input type="checkbox"/> To combine with other data The Greenness has been computed before the decommissioning of the previous project over Modis data. Now it's run over a 1 km resolution and needs to be upscale to 300 m over the CGLS S3 TOC product.			
Data formats and standards	<input type="checkbox"/> Text files - MS Word docs, .txt files, PDF, RTF, XML (Extensible Markup Language) <input type="checkbox"/> Numerical - SPSS, Stata, Excel <input type="checkbox"/> Multimedia - jpg / jpeg, gif, tiff, png, mpeg, mp4, QuickTime <input type="checkbox"/> Models – 3D, statistical <input type="checkbox"/> Software – Java, C, Python <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Discipline specific formats - Flexible Image Transport System (FITS) in astronomy, Crystallographic Information File (CIF) for crystallography <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify: NetCDF			
Origin of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Primary data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Secondary data Data are provided by the company VITO under the contract to produce other products. More information about the TOC, even though at 1Km			

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	and not 300m, can be found here Top Of Canopy Reflectances Copernicus Global Land Service			
Expected data volume	To be determined.			
Data utility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Research communities <input type="checkbox"/> Decision makers <input type="checkbox"/> Education <input type="checkbox"/> Economy <input type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Industry <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:			
Scientific impact	N/A.			
Data FAIRness				
Metadata	Climate and Forecast (CF) conventions v1.6.			
Openly accessible data	No			
Repositories of openly accessible data	N/A			
Preservation of openly accessible data	N/A			
Reusable data	No			
Purpose	<input type="checkbox"/> To reproduce and validate findings <input type="checkbox"/> To compare and combine with other data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To follow-up research on a specific area <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To develop new products/services <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:			
Repositories of reusable data	The process to disseminate results is currently under discussion.			
Preservation of reusable data	To be decided.			
Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)				
<i>Item</i>	<i>Partners owners & Other beneficiaries involved</i>	<i>Confidential</i>	<i>Type of protection or licensing action used</i>	<i>Protection or licensing actions used</i>
CGLS S3 TOC	Copernicus Global Land Service Partner: VITO	Yes	Copyright	Ad hoc licensing for the specific project.

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2.4.7 Use Case: Pangeo@RELIANCE

Use Case Name	Pangeo@RELIANCE
Main contact person	Jean laquinta & Anne Fouilloux
Description	<p>Extreme weather events and climate adaptation (biomass, local populations) looking at 3 aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determine conditions favourable to Rain-on-Snow (RoS) in Troms and Finnmark (Norway) using reanalysis data (ERA5, ERA5-land); • Assess Arctic browning with satellite data and derived vegetation indices (such Normalized Difference Vegetation Indices, Condition Vegetation Indices, etc.) or classifications (Global Land Cover); • Evaluate potential correlations between the occurrence of these extreme events and some types of Arctic vegetation dying (in particular mosses and lichens).
Data Summary	
Types of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Observational (e.g., sensor data, data from surveys) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Simulation (e.g., climate modelling data) <input type="checkbox"/> Derived or compiled (e.g., text mining, 3D models) <input type="checkbox"/> Reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures) <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:
Purpose of data collection/generation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To obtain information <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To share information <input type="checkbox"/> To keep on record <input type="checkbox"/> To make informed decisions <input type="checkbox"/> To develop a product <input type="checkbox"/> To improve a product <input type="checkbox"/> To combine with other data
Data formats and standards	<input type="checkbox"/> Text files - MS Word docs, .txt files, PDF, RTF, XML (Extensible Markup Language) <input type="checkbox"/> Numerical - SPSS, Stata, Excel <input type="checkbox"/> Multimedia - jpg / jpeg, gif, tiff, png, mpeg, mp4, QuickTime <input type="checkbox"/> Models – 3D, statistical <input type="checkbox"/> Software – Java, C, Python <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Discipline specific formats - Flexible Image Transport System (FITS) in astronomy, Crystallographic Information File (CIF) for crystallography <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify: netCDF, GRIB, Zarr
Origin of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Primary data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Secondary data Global Land Cover (classification), meteorological re-analysis
Expected data volume	5 TB

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Data utility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Research communities <input type="checkbox"/> Decision makers <input type="checkbox"/> Education <input type="checkbox"/> Economy <input type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Industry <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:
Scientific impact	Extreme events in the arctic are more and more frequent and have a strong impact on the local Sami population. Being able to accurately understand potential occurrences of extreme events to mitigate them (for instance change of route for reindeers to avoid ice over snow and lack of food).
Data FAIRness	
Metadata	CF convention
Openly accessible data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ERA5-Land (hourly data from 1950 to present, variable: '2m_temperature', 'snow_depth_water_equivalent', 'total_precipitation', geographical area: Nordic countries) • ERA5 (hourly data on single levels from 1959 to present ('2m_temperature', 'clear_sky_direct_solar_radiation_at_surface', 'mean_total_precipitation_rate', 'precipitation_type', 'snow_depth', 'total_precipitation')) • Copernicus Global Land Cover classification (fractional cover as described in Table-3 of Document-No. • CGLOPS1_PUM_LC100-V3, at highest resolution e.g. down to 10m, from 2015 or even earlier, if available, to present days),
Repositories of openly accessible data	http://reliance.adamplatform.eu https://registry.opendata.aws/ecmwf-era5/ https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-pressure-levels?tab=overview https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=overview https://lcviewer.vito.be/2015 https://worldcover2021.esa.int/ https://zenodo.org/record/5571936#.Y9tx00HMIuW
Preservation of openly accessible data	Data used as input are preserved by data providers. Data we produced will be archived in Zenodo and the Norwegian National Archive.
Reusable data	All data produced will be published in Zenodo and get a DOI. Data will contain appropriate domain specific metadata (CF-convention).

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Purpose	<input type="checkbox"/> To reproduce and validate findings <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To compare and combine with other data <input type="checkbox"/> To follow-up research on a specific area <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To develop new products/services <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:			
Repositories of reusable data	http://reliance.adamplatform.eu https://registry.opendata.aws/ecmwf-era5/ https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-pressure-levels?tab=overview https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=overview			
Preservation of reusable data	http://archive.norstore.no			
Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)				
<i>Item</i>	<i>Partners owners & Other beneficiaries involved</i>	<i>Confidential</i>	<i>Type of protection or licensing action used</i>	<i>Protection or licensing actions used</i>
Any dataset generated	University of Oslo Simula Research Laboratory	No	Copyright	CC-BY-4

2.4.8 Use Case: SAR on the Fly

Use Case Name	SAR on the Fly. SAR Application Ready on the Fly
Main contact person	Guido Lemoine
Description	Deploy GPU resources to process Sentinel-1 Level 1 Single Look Complex to Analysis Ready Data, in particular coherence, for use in land use monitoring.
Data Summary	
Types of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Observational (e.g., sensor data, data from surveys) <input type="checkbox"/> Simulation (e.g., climate modelling data) <input type="checkbox"/> Derived or compiled (e.g., text mining, 3D models) <input type="checkbox"/> Reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures) <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:
Purpose of data collection/generation	<input type="checkbox"/> To obtain information <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To share information <input type="checkbox"/> To keep on record <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To make informed decisions

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	<input type="checkbox"/> To develop a product <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To improve a product <input type="checkbox"/> To combine with other data Product (or rather service) improvement by allowing drastic speed up in ARD coherence production (at least factor 15). Special focus on sharing data in near real time crop monitoring in Ukraine, with output flowing onto the public eo4ua.org platform.
Data formats and standards	<input type="checkbox"/> Text files - MS Word docs, .txt files, PDF, RTF, XML (Extensible Markup Language) <input type="checkbox"/> Numerical - SPSS, Stata, Excel <input type="checkbox"/> Multimedia - jpg / jpeg, gif, tiff, png, mpeg, mp4, QuickTime <input type="checkbox"/> Models – 3D, statistical <input type="checkbox"/> Software – Java, C, Python <input type="checkbox"/> Discipline specific formats - Flexible Image Transport System (FITS) in astronomy, Crystallographic Information File (CIF) for crystallography <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify: Geospatial imagery (GeoTIFF)
Origin of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Primary data <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary data Sentinel-1 Level 1 Single Look Complex can be considered “primary data”, although it has been generated from Sentinel-1 Level 0 RAW data (i.e., it has undergone processing, but not analysis).
Expected data volume	Order of 2 TB towards the end of the project (primarily for Ukraine territory)
Data utility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Research communities <input type="checkbox"/> Decision makers <input type="checkbox"/> Education <input type="checkbox"/> Economy <input type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Industry <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:
Scientific impact	First time that continuous coherence time series (sept 2020 to now) are made available over an entire national territory for multi-annual analysis in crop area monitoring.
Data FAIRness	
Metadata	GeoJSON
Openly accessible data	Openly shared repository on samba mount at CloudFerro’s eo4ua.org initiative
Repositories of openly accessible data	At smb://data.eo4ua.org/eo4ua . Data is mirrored on Google Earth Engine catalog JRC/S1_COH_TEST

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Preservation of openly accessible data	At least until end of C-SCALE project. After that, permanent storage into Copernicus Data Access Service is likely, esp. since continuation is foreseen under new initiatives.			
Reusable data	Yes			
Purpose	<input type="checkbox"/> To reproduce and validate findings <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To compare and combine with other data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To follow-up research on a specific area <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To develop new products/services <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:			
Repositories of reusable data	Same as above			
Preservation of reusable data	Same as above			
Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)				
<i>Item</i>	<i>Partners owners & Other beneficiaries involved</i>	<i>Confidential</i>	<i>Type of protection or licensing action used</i>	<i>Protection or licensing actions used</i>
GPU software	The deployed GPU software is open sourced by CGI Estonia.	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Copyright • Open Source 	GPL 3.0

2.4.9 Use Case: NC4EC

Use Case Name	Solar nowcasting for energy communities
Main contact person	Lukas Prenner
Description	In order to optimize the energy consumption within energy communities, highly accurate satellite based solar power nowcasting technology is necessary. On the basis of the solar power nowcasting data the air conditions, heat pumps and the charging process of electric vehicles can be controlled, in order to optimize energy consumption within an energy community.
Data Summary	
Types of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Observational (e.g., sensor data, data from surveys) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Simulation (e.g., climate modelling data) <input type="checkbox"/> Derived or compiled (e.g., text mining, 3D models) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures) <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:
Purpose of data collection/generation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To obtain information <input type="checkbox"/> To share information <input type="checkbox"/> To keep on record

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	<input type="checkbox"/> To make informed decisions <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To develop a product <input type="checkbox"/> To improve a product <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To combine with other data
Data formats and standards	<input type="checkbox"/> Text files - MS Word docs, .txt files, PDF, RTF, XML (Extensible Markup Language) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Numerical - SPSS, Stata, Excel <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Multimedia - jpg / jpeg, gif, tiff, png, mpeg, mp4, QuickTime <input type="checkbox"/> Models – 3D, statistical <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Software – Java, C, Python <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Discipline specific formats - Flexible Image Transport System (FITS) in astronomy, Crystallographic Information File (CIF) for crystallography <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify: MATLAB
Origin of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Primary data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Secondary data
Expected data volume	12.5 Gbytes per day
Data utility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Research communities <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Decision makers <input type="checkbox"/> Education <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Economy <input type="checkbox"/> Public <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Industry <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:
Scientific impact	Solar power management and financial analysis for the use of solar produced energy in households. Taking into account the socio-economic figures –such as capital cost, renewable tariffs, gas/electricity-to-CO2 emission factors- we can estimate their impact in calculating the smart city economic value. Information provided by this use case, may be integrated into an urban planning which will support the inclusion of produced solar energy by PVs plants into the electricity grid.
Data FAIRness	
Metadata	Timestamp inside the filename
Openly accessible data	Meteosat 2gen, Copernicus atmosphere monitoring service
Repositories of openly accessible data	Maps
Preservation of openly accessible data	N/A
Reusable data	N/A

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Purpose	<input type="checkbox"/> To reproduce and validate findings <input type="checkbox"/> To compare and combine with other data <input type="checkbox"/> To follow-up research on a specific area <input type="checkbox"/> To develop new products/services <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:			
Repositories of reusable data	N/A			
Preservation of reusable data	N/A			
Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)				
<i>Item</i>	<i>Partners owners & Other beneficiaries involved</i>	<i>Confidential</i>	<i>Type of protection or licensing action used</i>	<i>Protection or licensing actions used</i>
Data products	EnergyFamily	Yes	Patents Trademarks Copyright	N/A

2.4.10 Use Case: DInSAR processing for GEP

Use Case Name	Cloud Processing of Differential Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar data for the Geohazards Exploitation Platform (GEP) users
Main contact person	Hervé Caumont COO, Terradue herve.caumont@terradue.com
Description	DInSAR processing chain for the generation of Earth deformation time series and mean velocity maps. Input (local cache): Copernicus Sentinel-1 SLC (Level-1) data products. Output : wrapped and unwrapped interferograms, Line of Sight (LOS) Displacement time series; Mean LOS Velocity; Temporal Coherence; Average scatterer elevation (Topography).
Data Summary	
Types of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Observational (e.g., sensor data, data from surveys) <input type="checkbox"/> Simulation (e.g., climate modelling data) <input type="checkbox"/> Derived or compiled (e.g., text mining, 3D models) <input type="checkbox"/> Reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures) <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify: Input (local cache): Copernicus Sentinel-1 SLC (Level-1) data products. Output : wrapped and unwrapped interferograms, Line of Sight (LOS) Displacement time series; Mean LOS Velocity; Temporal Coherence; Average scatterer elevation (Topography).

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Purpose of data collection/generation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To obtain information <input type="checkbox"/> To share information <input type="checkbox"/> To keep on record <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To make informed decisions <input type="checkbox"/> To develop a product <input type="checkbox"/> To improve a product <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To combine with other data https://eo4society.esa.int/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/TAT_2021_GEP_Training_distributed.pdf
Data formats and standards	<input type="checkbox"/> Text files - MS Word docs, .txt files, PDF, RTF, XML (Extensible Markup Language) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Numerical - CSV <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Multimedia - GeoTIFF, png <input type="checkbox"/> Models – 3D, statistical <input type="checkbox"/> Software – Java, C, Python <input type="checkbox"/> Discipline specific formats - Flexible Image Transport System (FITS) in astronomy, Crystallographic Information File (CIF) for crystallography <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify: Geospatial data formats
Origin of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Primary data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Secondary data https://sentinels.copernicus.eu/web/sentinel/missions/sentinel-1
Expected data volume	1 to 10 TB depending on level of user activity over the period 1st Semester 2023
Data utility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Research communities <input type="checkbox"/> Decision makers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Education <input type="checkbox"/> Economy <input type="checkbox"/> Public <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Industry <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:
Scientific impact	https://geohazards-tep.eu/#!pages/initiative Several scientific publications each year referencing DinSAR products generated by GEP users
Data FAIRness	
Metadata	OWSContext https://www.ogc.org/standards/owc Service specific metadata formats https://docs.terradue.com/geohazards-tep/tutorials/index.html
Openly accessible data	When shared publicly on GEP by the GEP user. GEP users have the ownership of their generated data products.

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	Free access to GEP open data from: https://geohazards-tep.eu/geobrowser/?id=globalapp and from: https://geohazards-tep.eu/geobrowser/?id=epos			
Repositories of openly accessible data	Some results published on Zenodo https://zenodo.org/communities/geohazards-exploitation-platform/			
Preservation of openly accessible data	As long as user's GEP subscription runs. 6 months up until the end of a GEP user subscription Sponsorship programs can extend the data preservation policy on GEP (e.g., for the EPOS Community results on GEP).			
Reusable data	Most EO-based products generated via GEP are meant for post-processing & analysis, either by the GEP user generating it or by partners /third-party.			
Purpose	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To reproduce and validate findings <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To compare and combine with other data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To follow-up research on a specific area <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To develop new products/services <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:			
Repositories of reusable data	cf. "Openly accessible data"			
Preservation of reusable data	cf. "Preservation of openly accessible data"			
Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)				
<i>Item</i>	<i>Partners owners & Other beneficiaries involved</i>	<i>Confidential</i>	<i>Type of protection or licensing action used</i>	<i>Protection or licensing actions used</i>
DiNSAR processing data products	Terradue ¹⁰	No	Copyright	https://geohazards-tep.eu/downloadFiles/EULA-GEP.pdf

2.5 WP5 Capacity building, dissemination, and exploitation

Main contact person	Sebastian Luna-Valero
Description	Outreach and dissemination material, documentation related to C-SCALE services, and material for user support and training.
Data Summary	

¹⁰ GEP user guidance for Citation: *The InSAR processing was performed on the Geohazards Exploitation Platform (geohazards-tep.eu) operated by Terradue (www.terradue.com).*

For products generated by processing of Copernicus Sentinel data: *Contains Copernicus Sentinel data.*

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Types of data	<input type="checkbox"/> Observational (e.g., sensor data, data from surveys) <input type="checkbox"/> Simulation (e.g., climate modelling data) <input type="checkbox"/> Derived or compiled (e.g., text mining, 3D models) <input type="checkbox"/> Reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documents (e.g., publications, use case applications), slides (e.g. project presentations), flyers (e.g. promotional material), spreadsheets (e.g. capacity allocation tables), web pages (e.g. news items on the C-SCALE website, tutorials on GitHub), wiki pages (e.g. user documentation and WP coordination pages on the C-SCALE space in EGI confluence), videos (YouTube recordings for user tutorials)
Purpose of data collection/generation	<input type="checkbox"/> To obtain information <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To share information <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To keep on record <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To make informed decisions <input type="checkbox"/> To develop a product <input type="checkbox"/> To improve a product <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To combine with other data These data include material that can be reused to present project's approaches and outcomes, service management implementation and for education & training and support purposes for end users.
Data formats and standards	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Text files - MS Word docs, .txt files, PDF, RTF, XML (Extensible Markup Language) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Numerical - SPSS, Stata, Excel <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Multimedia - jpg / jpeg, gif, tiff, png, mpeg, mp4, QuickTime <input type="checkbox"/> Models – 3D, statistical <input type="checkbox"/> Software – Java, C, Python <input type="checkbox"/> Discipline specific formats - Flexible Image Transport System (FITS) in astronomy, Crystallographic Information File (CIF) for crystallography
Origin of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Primary data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Secondary data Created as a result of work done within the project.
Expected data volume	MB (megabyte) The maximum size of an individual document in the set is in the range of tens of MB, the total number of files is not expected to extend to thousands of files.
Data utility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers

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	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Research communities <input type="checkbox"/> Decision makers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Education <input type="checkbox"/> Economy <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Industry <input type="checkbox"/> Other Anyone interested in developing Copernicus or Earth Observation applications on an open, EOSC-compliant platform can benefit from the documents in this collection. Cross-Project initiatives and Knowledge base contribution in the area of Open Science and beyond.
Scientific impact	N/A.
Data FAIRness	
Metadata	N/A.
Openly accessible data	Publications, outreach material, user documentation, user forum, and user training.
Repositories of openly accessible data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publications: Open Access Journals (e.g., https://www.tandfonline.com/tbed20) • Outreach material: https://c-scale.eu/ • User documentation: https://wiki.c-scale.eu/C-SCALE • User forum: https://github.com/c-scale-community/discussions/discussions • User training: https://github.com/c-scale-community and https://www.youtube.com/@c-scale_project
Preservation of openly accessible data	Available from the moment they are created and preserved for at least 5 years after the end of the project.
Reusable data	Project deliverables, publications, and user training.
Purpose	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To reproduce and validate findings <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To compare and combine with other data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To follow-up research on a specific area <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To develop new products/services <input type="checkbox"/> Other:
Repositories of reusable data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publications: Open Access Journals (e.g., https://www.tandfonline.com/journals/tbed20) • User training: https://github.com/c-scale-community and https://www.youtube.com/@c-scale_project
Preservation of reusable data	Available from the moment they are created and preserved for at least 5 years after the end of the project.
Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)	

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<i>Item</i>	<i>Partners owners & Other beneficiaries involved</i>	<i>Confidential</i>	<i>Type of protection or licensing action used</i>	<i>Protection or licensing actions used</i>
Project slides, publications, outreach material, user documentation.	C-SCALE Consortium	No	Copyright	CC BY 4.0
Use case applications, capacity allocation table, WP coordination pages on the C-SCALE space in EGI confluence.	C-SCALE Consortium	Yes	Copyright	N/A
C-SCALE tutorials: snakemake introduction, openEO introduction	C-SCALE Consortium	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Copyright • Open source 	AGPL-3.0
C-SCALE user forum	General public	No	Copyright	N/A

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3 Conclusions

With its participation in the Open Research Data Pilot, the C-SCALE project is required to create a DMP, make it publicly available and update it throughout the runtime of the project. Since the nature of the project is rather technical and focuses on federating services, not many research data are produced. Therefore, the original DMP template from the EC was simplified to provide the information in a more comprehensive way.

This document has provided the second and final version of the DMP by giving details on the data types that are collected and generated per Work Package (WP), whether they will be shared with the public and how, whether they can be reused and how, and how they will be preserved during and after the end of the project, based on the consortium's knowledge until present (M26). Some decisions on the availability and reusability of the data, and more specifically the ones that the use cases produce, are yet to be made as once the maturity of these use cases allows it. In addition, in this second version, information about the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) of the C-SCALE data has been included.

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